

EMPLOYEE RELATIONS AND JOB SATISFACTION IN AKWA IBOM STATE CIVIL SERVICE, NIGERIA

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*Employee,
Employee
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Abstract: *This study examined employee relations and job satisfaction in Akwa Ibom State Civil Service. The objectives of this study were to find out the employee relations practices carried out in Akwa Ibom State Civil Service, assess if employee relations enhance job satisfaction in Akwa Ibom State Civil Service, determine the extent to which employee relations practices influence job satisfaction in Akwa Ibom State Civil Service, examine the challenges affecting effective employee relations in Akwa Ibom State Civil Service, find out other factors that influence job satisfaction, and propose strategies for improving employee relations and enhance job satisfaction in Akwa Ibom State Civil Service. Survey research design was adopted for this study, with questionnaire as the major instrument for gathering data. The population of the study comprised all civil servants in Akwa Ibom State Civil Service which was 55,120. The sample size for the study was determined at 400, using Taro Yamane's formula. Anchored on Equity Theory, and Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory, the study revealed that majority of respondents (60%) pointed to building reputable organisational culture as employee practices implemented in Akwa Ibom State Civil Service. Furthermore, employees of Akwa Ibom State Civil Service agreed that the current employee relations practice does not enhance job satisfaction. Findings revealed that majority of respondents (78%) agreed that to a great extent employee relations influences job satisfaction. The study concludes that although Akwa Ibom State Civil Service has established employee relations structures, their implementation remains inconsistent. It was recommended that government should carry out periodic employee relations audit exercise in order to determine current employee relations practices for enhancement of job satisfaction, among other recommendations.*

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Introduction

Employee relations simply refer to the efforts, policies and practices that an organisation uses to manage the relationship between employers and employees. According to Armstrong (2020), employee relations focus on maintaining a positive, productive, and respectful working environment. These include communication quality, grievance handling, participation in decision making, workplace fairness, and the general climate of employer-employee engagement. Udom and Archibong (2021), stated that effective employee relations promote cooperation, reduce conflict, enhance morale, and contribute significantly to job satisfaction. The notion that employees have high relevance in organisations significantly determine the degree of success or failures organisations record, tends to be both truthful and dependable. Organisations that are committed to achieving better performance, greater effectiveness and competitive edge over rivals see employees as “assets” that have higher and sustainable value are described as “ends” in themselves as opposed to being used as ‘means to an end. This is why Dessler (2017) asserts that successful organisations depend on the (high) performance of their workers to meet their set aims and objectives.

The concept of employee relations has gained improved research interest in contemporary studies especially on how effective communication can better handle staff treatment

at the work place, contribute to productivity or satisfaction. The concept builds more reliance on the functionality of strategic interaction between employees in organisations and how they build strong relationships that affect different concerns and parties. According to Bratton and Gold (2017), the key aspects of employee relations are in the areas of communication, conflict resolution, employee engagement and motivation, workplace policies, labour union interactions, employee rights and compliance. These key areas ensure clear, transparent, and consistent communication between management and employees. It also addresses misunderstandings, grievances, and disputes fairly and promptly, creating a work environment where employees feel valued, supported, and motivated to perform well.

Effective communication within an organization as part of employee relations creates the feelings and sense of belonging among employees leaving in them the conviction that they are important and valuable. Gennard and Judge (2020) note that where organisations sincerely listen to their employees, they feel more valued and as a result, offer themselves willingly and readily to engaged in driving organizational success. Daprix and Faghan (2011) stress that transparent communication is critical at work place. This is because, for them, such interactive feat creates trust about management on the part of employees and makes them carry out assigned tasks with joyful attention and excellent

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achievement. More so, another area of employee relations that receive greater concern is that of psychological contract. Discussing this notion, Leat (2014) notes that employee relation distinguishes the importance of values in employee relationship within an organisation. The author argues that equity, justice, dignity and trust are part of the values often described as fundamental to the effectiveness of the employee relations, and achievement of organisations' objectives. Schein (1988) cited in Leat (2014) suggests that between employers and employees, exists implicit contractual relationship derived from a series of assumptions held by both employers and employees about the nature of their relationship need to be characterised by the concern for equity and justice which requires the communication of sufficient information about changes and development; reciprocation or loyalty between employees and employers with a degree of fruitful employment and job security, and value in addition to recognition of employees' contribution by employers.

Job satisfaction, on the other hand, refers to the extent to which employees feel fulfilled, motivated, and content with their work. It is influenced by factors such as remuneration, work environment, management style, recognition, job security, interpersonal relationships, and opportunities for growth. According to Ekong (2018), the recent observation in Akwa Ibom State indicate concerns about employee morale, workplace motivation, disputes between labour unions and

government, and perceptions of unfair labour practices. These issues highlight the direct link between employee relations and job satisfaction, reinforcing the need for systematic study to understand how employee relations strategies influence job satisfaction in the state civil service. Half (2019), attempted to describe the relationship between employee relations and job satisfaction, in their recurrent discussion about organisational communication, marketing communication and public relations at the workplace. Strength of the discussions suggests that poor employee relations in organisations can cause lack of job satisfaction which can invariably affect productivity. Job satisfaction in the view of Okorie (2019), is the feeling of the employees towards the workplace situation about their jobs. It entails an individual's subjective perspective (perception) which involves the way they think of or consider and the employing organisation. Moreover, job satisfaction is the pleasurable emotional state that results from the achievement of job values (Courtney & Younkyoung, 2017).

Brief History of Akwa Ibom State Civil Service

According to Udoh (2017), the Akwa Ibom State Civil Service has its roots in the creation of Akwa Ibom State on September 23, 1987, when it was carved out of Cross River State by the military administration of General Ibrahim Babangida. The establishment of the civil service was crucial for the administration and governance of the new state. The Civil Service is a bureaucracy, a type of

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organisation designed to accomplish large-scale administrative task through the systematic coordination of many individuals' works. It is broadly characterised by regular activities assigned to individuals as fixed duties, hierarchy, consistent system of roles, and standards, personality of officials, employment based on technical qualifications and protection from arbitrary dismissal. It is also characterised by the possibility of attaining the highest hierarchy of technical or administrative efficiency and many other characteristics. Under the current Akwa Ibom State Civil Service arrangement, the Head of Civil Service is responsible to ensuring the overall coordination of the entire Civil Service. The Head of the Civil Service oversees the entire spectrum of government activities to ensure that those activities take intended direction. There are numerous service commissions such as: the Civil Service Commission, The Local Government Service Commission, the Judiciary Service Commission, and the Board of Statutory Corporations. These commissions are under the dictate of the law, vested with specific but variant responsibilities of appointment, promotions, transfers and disciplinary control of its employees.

According to the Akwa Ibom State Civil Service Handbook (2020), the department of Establishment serve as the principal personnel department in charge of personnel policy advice, industrial relations, pensions, trainings and implementation of approved service conditions, programmes, and reviews of procedures and

practices. At the head of the entire service, is the Executive Governor, functioning as the Head of government. Sandwiched around (inserted into service are numerous ministries, extra-ministerial departments, bureaus, agencies and boards, which are within the civil service structure. These administrative organisations have bureaucratic characteristics and are staffed by employees with different levels of skills, knowledge, attitudes, and experiences. There are also political, administrative and professional appointees in these organisations. (i.e, the civil service organs). They all discharge their obligations, utilizing available resources, like the civil servants to achieve the goals of the government.

The term Bureaucracy connotes the general formal structure element depicting a typical human organisation particularly that structure and personnel of a government organisation like the civil service. A German sociologist, Max Weber leads the orientation of scholars towards a better understanding of the term through his definition. In that effort, he conceived the term in two perspectives: the social mechanism that maximises efficiently in administration; and a formal organization with specific features including the regular activities required for the purpose of the structure are distributed in fixed ways as official duties, specific spheres of competence have been marked off as part of a systematic division of labour, all operations are governed by consistent system of abstract rules, the officials are subject to strict and systematic

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discipline and control in the conduct of their offices, there is consistency in the application of rules to specific cases, the arrangement or constitution of offices follows a principle of hierarchy, which is, 'each lower office is under the control and supervision of higher one, officials are subject to authority on their impersonal official obligation, candidates are selected on the basis of technical qualifications, and being a bureaucratic officer constitutes a career and there is a system of promotion which is according to seniority or merit, or even both. Weber sums that a fully developed bureaucracy has the advantage of speed, precision, unambiguity, continuity, direction, unity, strict coordination and reduction of friction, materials and costs. Stillman (1976) cited in Udom (2010) argues however that, inefficiency, red tape, stupidity, secrecy, smugness, aggressiveness, and self-interest, are emotionally commanding terms commonly used in the description of bureaucracy like the civil service. The key features of the Akwa Ibom State Civil Service are the Public Service Commission, Head of Service, Training and Development, Pension and Welfare. The Public Service Commission oversees recruitment of staff, promotions, and discipline, the Head of Service is responsible for administration and coordination of government ministries, Training and Development arranged regular workshops and training programs to enhance efficiency while the Pension and Welfare made efforts to clear pension arrears and improve worker's condition.

According to Ikpe (2019), The Akwa Ibom State Civil Service faces challenges such as bureaucratic inefficiency, political interference, and pension arrears. However, ongoing reforms, including e-governance initiatives and staff welfare improvements, aim to make it more effective and transparent. The Akwa Ibom Civil Service being a bureaucracy may be challenged by numerous realities including employee relations especially in the area of information flow, staff welfare, staff treatment, staff participation and other employee-advantaged practices. The concern of this work is to examine the whether employee relations influences employee job satisfaction in the civil service.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the critical role of the civil service in driving public administration in Akwa Ibom State, evidence suggests that employee relations remain weak and inconsistent. Reports of poor communication between management and staff, delayed or irregular promotion processes, inadequate reward systems, and limited involvement of employees in decision making processes have created discontent within the workforce. Furthermore, recurrent industrial disputes between labour unions and government authorities reflect deeper unresolved issues in employee relations. These issues may undermine job satisfaction, reduce productivity, and negatively affect service delivery to the public. There is also a lack of empirical data on how employee relations practices within the Akwa Ibom State Civil Service influence job

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satisfaction among employees. This gap makes it difficult for policymakers to design strategic interventions for improving morale and productivity in the civil service. This study, therefore, seeks to examine these issues and provide insights for improved management practices.

Objectives of the Study

This study seeks to:

- i. find out the employee relations practices carried out in the Akwa Ibom State Civil Service;
- ii. assess if employee relations enhance job satisfaction in the Akwa Ibom State Civil Service;
- iii. determine the extent to which employee relations practices influence job satisfaction in the Akwa Ibom State Civil Service;

Research Questions

The following questions guided this study:

- i. What employee relations practices are carried out in the Akwa Ibom State Civil Service?
- ii. Do employee relations practices enhance job satisfaction in the Akwa Ibom State Civil Service?
- iii. To what extent do employee relations practices influence job satisfaction in the Akwa Ibom State Civil Service?

Literature Review

Gennard and Judge (2022) in Chartered Institute of Personal and Development (CIPD), conceives the concept of employee relations as a broad term that includes many issues from collective bargaining, negotiations, employment legislation to more recent considerations in areas

like; work-life balance, equal opportunities and managing diversity. It comprises the practices or initiatives with which organisations ensure greater happiness and productivity of their employees. In modern organisations, employee relations is even much broader a concept that takes into cognizance a kind of work environment that intensifies the satisfaction of the needs of individual employee's morale, building reputable organisational culture, conveying expectations (from internal stakeholders, meeting staff expectations on welfare, financial gratification (Okorie, 2019).

Employees are rated as an organisation's most crucial resources and described as very valuable assets organizations have. The kind and degree of work carried out within organisations depend largely on the nature of employees. This therefore has a direct influence on the level of productivity, success or failure such organisations record. Therefore, sustaining a crop of healthy employee via strategic employee relations practices is a pre-requisite for organization that seek to achieve sustainable growth and success (Sequeira & Dhriti, 2015).

An effective employee relation involves the process of creating and cultivating a motivated and productive workforce needed for organisational success. According to Udom and Archibong (2021), this is necessary in keeping the dynamics of employer-employee relationship fruitful over a sustained period of time. It entails the relationships between employers and employees in organisation. Employee relations

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also include giving opportunities for employees' participation in management decisions, strategic communications and policy formulation as a means of improving cooperation and regulating of grievances as well as minimising workplace conflicts. Gennard and Judge (2012) cited in Leat (2014: p.14) defines the concept of employee relations as the "study of rules, regulations and agreements by which employees are managed both as individuals and as a collective group, the priority given to the individual as opposed to the collective relationship varying from company to company depending upon the values of management". This is therefore concerned with organisation's efforts to gaining people's (employees') commitment towards the achievement of the business goal and objectives of organisations in various situations.

Employee relations focus on the management of the relationship between the employees and the employers in order to heighten their commitment, passion and performance (Hameed, 2019). Mike (2018) noted that employee relations involve the apparatus or platform for ensuring or encouraging employee loyalty to organisations and a higher stake of productivity. Cole and Kelly (2019) argue that employee relations in organisations in constitutes the backbone for staff motivation especially in achieving so much within available resources of time and money. Employee relations in this aspect, is positioned to coordinate employees and encourage them to offer their best in organizational growth and success.

Employee relations are noted for its contribution in employee recognition, management policy development and interpretation, for organisations. Such relations also foster problem solving and dispute resolution efforts put up by organisations. Here, employees see themselves as important, valuable and significant and thus avoid to the barest minimum, instances or issues that could culminate in conflicts or crises (Sequeira & Dhiru, 2015). Much of the work of employee relations centers on financial gratifications and employment related issues of workers in companies. Blyton and Turnbull (2018) note that employee relations enhance pay-back bargains, and other dealings like recruitment practices, terms and conditions of employment, issues arising from employment, providing employees with opportunities, platforms and need for communicating within the workplace.

Employee relations is concerned with maintaining employee-employer relation, which contributes to satisfactory productivity, increase in employee morale and motivation. Smidts, VanRiel and Pruyne (2017) in the discussion of employee relations point out the place of communication as a major component. Pratt (2020) considers communication to be a crucial and feasible management instrument to affect underlying motives for employees' identification. Important concerns here lie on how employees communicate with management and themselves. Employee relations led to business success. As the famous quote from Richard Branson (2014),

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who says, “take care of your employees, and they will take care of your business”. Good communication boosts employee morale, engagement, and productivity. Employee who feels informed and heard are more likely to be committed to the work and the organisation.

Gennard and Judge (2022) emphasises on the importance of non-monetary incentives in boosting employee engagement and performance, it reveals a strategic focus on non-cash rewards can generate significant return on investment in terms of employee engagement, performance improvement and financial results. In the issue of employee communication as part of employee relations, he notes that employing different communication strategies are successful tips for organisations to strengthen members’ identification, expressiveness and valuable contribution. He recommended that organisations should ensure an increase in members’ involvement with the company’s mission and vision, while strengthening employees’ emotional bonds between themselves and management.

Employee relations in the area of communication helps members staff in organisations identify with their organisations through the transmission of messages conveying their goals, values and achievements. This also helps in the provision of information in the form of guidelines that dictate the behaviours, actions and inactions of employees within the organisation. Sue and Fitzpatrick (2022), stated that in clarity of purpose in an organisation,

effective employee communication must be clear, relevant, and aligned with business objectives. Communication should help employees understand not just what is happening, but why it matters to them. Communication should be a two-way thing to be successful, communication is not just about sending messages but also about listening and engaging with employees, feedback loops are essential for building trust and improving workplace relationships. Sue and Fitzpatrick (2022), stated that organisations should use a mix of traditional and digital communication channels to reach employees effectively, the choice of channels should depend on the audience and the nature of the message.

In the discussion of employee relations, psychological contract and its fulfilment, has been identified as an important element. Chang (2015) notes that the effectiveness of employee relations practices is likely to be associated with positive and high-potential employees’ attitudes. High-potential (promising) employees perceive, value, and react to managements’ recognition of contributions and efforts differently. Within the psychological contract’s literature, these dynamics have been studied in terms of employee perceived inducements and employee-felt obligations to contribute to the organization. Psychological contract has to do with the reelection about employee perceptions of the rules involved in the exchange relationship between the employer and the employee, as well as the resources with which the exchange is

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made. Psychological contract describes the belief employees they owe their employer. It also entails such belief have about what employers owe them in return in their continuous employment contract (Shore, Coyle-Shapiro, & Tetrick, 2012).

Hoppock (1925) cited in Aziri (2011) defines job satisfaction as any combination of psychological and environmental circumstances that cause a person truthfully to state the level of satisfaction with job. This approach considers job satisfaction under the influence of various external factors as well as internal factors which concern basically the feelings of employees in relations to their work. Job satisfaction at this instance indicates a set of factors that cause a feeling of satisfaction. According to Spector (2022), job satisfaction is a complex and multifaceted concept influenced by various psychological, organisational, and social factors. He defines job satisfaction as an employee's overall attitude toward their job, whether they feel positively or negatively about it, it reflects how well a job meets an individual's needs, values, and expectations.

Job satisfaction has a lot to do with the feelings employees have towards their workplace situation as typified in contemporary literature, it involves both affective (emotional) responses and cognitive (rational) evaluations of work. Employees develop satisfaction based on experiences, perceptions, and personal values. In the view of Brief and Weiss (2022), job satisfaction measures employees' feeling and

emotion towards their job conditions as important organizational stakeholders. This goes a long way in determining the level of commitment and dedication to task. Tansel and Gazioglu (2013) citing Locke (1976) define job satisfaction as individuals' subjective valuation of different aspects of their job. Higher job satisfactions are mostly attached to improvements in the objective aspects of the job either because of reduced expectations or because dissatisfying aspects of the job are downplayed, while pleasing aspects are given greater weight. The relationship of job satisfaction to productivity, quit and absenteeism in the work place is emphasized by a number of authors.

Robinson and Morrison (2000) and Leat (2014) indicate that job satisfaction is as good a predictor of quits and absenteeism as wages are. They point out that individuals leave low-satisfaction jobs for high-satisfaction-jobs. Thus, job satisfaction also gives useful information about job turnover in addition to overall organisational or company performance and productivity. It also leads to higher productivity, lower turnover, and better mental health while job dissatisfaction can result in absenteeism, burnout, and workplace conflicts. For these reasons, researchers see the need to study the aspects of job satisfaction. Belfield and Wei (2004), note the different aspects of job satisfaction which are mostly considered by scholars and these include: gender, age, wages, growth comparison, income and unemployment,

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employment size and work environment, job matching and service sector, among other areas. Spector (2022) stated that several factors influence job satisfaction such as the work environment, supportive management, fair policies, and workplace culture. The job characteristics; task variety, autonomy, and meaningful work. Compensation and benefits; fair pay and rewards aligned with performance, social relationships with co-worker and supervisor relationships, and personal factors which has to do with individual personality, expectations, and career goals. Employees are more satisfied when they find purpose in their work and also, have control over tasks and decision-making increases satisfaction, being acknowledge for efforts boosts morale and giving the opportunity for learning and promotion enhance motivation. Employees who enjoy their work are more engaged.

According to Lokesh and Kumar (2024), job satisfaction is a positive emotional state that results from an employee's evaluation of their job experiences. It reflects how much an individual likes, enjoys, or is content with their job. It includes both affective components (feelings, about the job) and cognitive components (beliefs about job conditions such as pay, supervision, and work environment). In simple terms, job satisfaction is how employees feel about their job, based on whether their expectations and work experiences are being met.

There are several factors that determine job satisfaction. According to Putra (2023), work

environment and the working conditions is one of such factors. A safe, well-reserved workplace and positive coworker relationships consistently predict higher job satisfaction. Workers are also more satisfied with works that are interesting and at the same time challenging but also require them working long hours, (Lee 2023). Working long hours do not anguish employees provided they are paid in commensurate measures to the work load specified in their assignments and they keep climbing the ladder of workplace hierarchy. Dissatisfaction ensured when workers work long hours and are forced to do so without accompanying rewards.

Another job satisfaction determinant is pay, compensation and benefits. Alkhateeb (2025), stated that fairness and competitiveness of salary and benefits remain strong predictors of satisfaction and intention to stay. It is a major determinant of employee's satisfaction at work. There is also leadership, style and supervisory support factor. Perceived supervisor support, transformational leadership, and quality of line management have large, replicable effects on employee's satisfaction.

Also, career development and promotion opportunities determine job satisfaction. According to Putra (2023), access to training, clear promotion pathways and perceived career prospects raise job satisfaction, especially among younger and mid-career staff. Availability of advancement opportunities, job autonomy, task variety and meaningful work (job

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characteristics) are also linked with higher intrinsic satisfaction.

Furthermore, recognition, rewards/feedback and work-life balance, flexibility (including remote/hybrid work gives satisfaction to employee. Gazi (2024) explains that frequent, meaningful recognition (not just pay) and constructive feedback improve satisfaction. Also, flexibility schedules and remote/hybrid arrangements are important modern determinants of satisfaction. Employees find satisfaction in jobs that are interesting, challenging, and provide opportunities for growth, while money isn't the only motivator, fair compensation significantly affects job satisfaction.

And lastly, job security, organisational stability and culture determines job satisfaction. Perceived job insecurity lowers satisfaction; secure employment or predictable contracts increase it. Also, a supportive, inclusive culture and good person-organisation fit are associated with sustained job satisfaction. (Lee 2023). Employee with stable employment report and a positive, ethical, inclusive culture would have job satisfaction and, a positive work culture with good peer relationships enhances satisfaction. Robbinson and Morrison (2020) explains that the more important factors that are conducive to job satisfaction are mentally challenging works, equitable rewards, supportive working conditions and supporting colleague. Employees are in preference of jobs that give them latitude to exhibit their skills and abilities to offer a

variety of work. They need freedom and feedback on how well their actions are noticed and described as contributory to growth of the company These features and observations make mentally demanding work more challenging. This is also because works with little challenges create room for laxity and boredom, even though work with too much challenge create frustration and feeling of failure. Within the circumstances of moderate challenging task, employees derive great pleasurable experience and satisfaction (Udom, 2010).

Employee Relations in Contemporary Corporate Organisations

Employee relations depict the specific ways whereby organisations or companies interacts with the staff, delivers policy information and works to create a more productive workplace. By not creating good policies for employee relations, you are creating issues within your company that could stop growth and effect your future success. Organisations that understand the objectives of employee relations, are more apt and focused in utilizing appropriate resources, time and putting them into good policies. Root (2017) considers some objectives employee relations in organisations as discussed below:

i.Charity

Creating and structuring policies that present company information, such as the proper way to submit a time card/book in organisations as well as the list of employee benefits, helps in ensuring clarity between the company and staff in the aspect of expectations and job delivery. When

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employees understand what management expects and how to work within the structure of a company, the workplace becomes more efficient. Creating confusion as a result of inadequate dissemination of important information to employees, can constitute a bane in the progress rate of the company and in most cases, lead to a drop in productivity and increased turnover among the staff.

ii. Employee Retention

Companies or organisations that focus on effective employee relations, create a corporate culture. Corporate policies that focus on strategic employee relations, help to increase employee retention. This is because as Rose (2015) notes, company turnover costs money in recruiting new employees, training new employees and getting new employees up to speed quickly. Through the development of policies that address employees' needs and help to make the staff feel respected, there increased likelihood that such company or organization will experience reduced levels of turnover. Some employee relations policies that encourage employee retention can be leave allowances, health benefits with counseling options, retirement programmes and plans, among others.

iii. Legal Issues

The federal, state and local governments have laws regarding employment and treatment of employees. Some potentials legal issues include discrimination in the workplace and harassment. Employee policy manual should have made with outlines of what company's policy is concerning

legal issues like those mentioned here. It should also address the best ways for employees to report violations and the penalties involved for people who violate company rules or mandated laws. The objective of employee relations in this instance is to create a legal framework that protects the company and employee while creating a productive workplace.

iv. Company Growth

Employee relations activities include annual employee reviews and the ongoing development of employees through training and managerial guidance. When the company and employees work together on developing employee careers, the employees benefit from a clear path to promotion and advancement in the company. The company benefits because future management candidates are identified, and the necessary resources can be applied to training those employees that will guide the future success of the company.

Employee relations (management-employee relationship) are necessary if an organization targets satisfaction in areas of performance and level or employee engagement. Autonomy of the employees in their work domain versus hierarchical control by the management towards the aims of the firm need to be tackled in a balanced dimension and degree. This is consequent upon the nature of effect it can create on productivity and loyalty of workers. For this reason, strategic employee relations practices are important (Tansel & Gazieglu, 2013). The implication here is the positive relationship or

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influence employee relations has on organisation productivity and performance.

Factors of Employee Relations

According to Mikkelson, York, and Arritola (2019), employee relations refer to the interactions, relationships, and communication patterns between employers and employees in an organisation. Strong employee relations contribute to higher morale, productivity, and organisational commitment. These key variables influencing employee relations include:

- i) **Communication:** Effective communication promotes trust, reduces conflict, and ensures employees are informed about expectations, changes, and organisational goals. Open communication channels encourage feedback and keep resolve misunderstandings early.
- ii) **Leadership Style:** Leadership behaviour strongly affects how employees perceive fairness, support, and respect within the organization. Democratic and transformational leadership styles tend to foster better employee relations than autocratic styles.
- iii) **Employee Voice and Participation:** Employees' ability to express opinions, participate in decisions, and contribute to policy formulation improves satisfaction and reduces conflict. Participation promotes ownership of work processes.
- iv) **Organisational Justice (Fairness):** Perceptions of fairness in procedures (procedural justice, treatment (interactional justice), and outcomes (distributive justice) are

key to strong employee-employer relationships. Fairness reduces conflict and increases trust.

- v) **Working Conditions:** A safe, healthy, and supportive work environment fosters positive employee relations. Poor physical or psychological working conditions create tension, absenteeism, and dissatisfaction.
- vi) **Rewards and Recognition:** According to Brun and Dugas (2020), reward systems, both financial and non-financial play a crucial role in motivating employees and strengthening employer-employee relationships. Recognition satisfies employees' need for appreciation and belonging.
- vii) **Conflict Management:** Organisations that have clear mechanisms for preventing and resolving conflict maintain healthier relationships. Conflict resolution practices influence employees' trust in management. (Rahim, 2017).
- viii) **Training and Career Development:** According to Park and Johnson (2019), when employees perceive strong support for learning and career advancement, they build positive relationships with the organisation and show higher engagement and loyalty.
- ix) **Employee Well-being:** Support for physical, emotional, and mental well-being such as work life balance and stress management strengthens employee relations and reduces turnover intentions. (Rahim, 2017).

The Need for Employee Job Satisfaction

According to Armstrong (2020), job satisfaction is the fulfillment which an employee feels in

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relation to their jobs and work place. It brings the question, whether the employee is happy or content at their jobs. An employee may be measuring their satisfaction in financial, non-financial or psychological contract terms. Job satisfaction degree levels of people range from extreme dissatisfaction to extreme satisfaction. For successful operation, companies need satisfied employees because employee satisfaction can lead to the commitment, conscientiousness and honesty of an employee, which in turn relate to their job performance (Gruban, 2010). In achieving employee satisfaction, the work environment plays a crucial role since it affects the life of individuals, their behaviour, perception and performance. (Barter 2011).

On the other hand, it is evident that organisations that maintain good relations with their employees are likely to experience increased profits, improved customer delivery, minimal resistance to change, dedicated and motivated staff who achieve organisational objectives. Due to job satisfaction, performance of the organisation has been affected resulting to increased employee turnovers, decreased profits and performance standards in the competitive business environment in the recent past. Other aspects that enhanced job satisfaction included; training of employees, open communication and timely introduction of change. Half (2019) submits that poor workplace relationships, denial of empowerment or influence, lack of work-life balance, absence of growth prospects,

the work isn't interesting or meaningful, and feeling of being unappreciated by employers are some of the factors that affect and lead to job dissatisfaction. And countering these negatively impactful factors, organisations are on the verge of ensuring satisfaction for their employees and also emerging in the endless competition in business. Job satisfaction factors also include the amount of recognition and praise an employee receives from management. A recent study by ADP showed that two thirds of UK workers do not feel valued and many of them would consider leaving for a new opportunity because of this.

Cited in Half (2019: p10) Melanie Robinson, Senior Director of Sales and Marketing at ADP, observed that: "ultimately, it is about investing in your people. With more years of service, employees will offer their companies more experience and skill and this should be recognized and valued, or employees can begin to lack purpose". In this instance, the remedy for unhappy workers can be something as simple as verbal praise, and even go as far as promotions, awards and salary increases.

Theoretical Framework

Two theories, the Equity Theory and Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory was adopted in this study.

The Equity Theory

According to Essien (2020), Equity Theory was developed by J. Stacey Adams in 1963, it is one of the foundational frameworks explaining employee motivation, fairness perceptions and workplace attitude. The theory argues that employees evaluate the fairness of their work

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environment by comparing the ratio of their inputs (effort, skills, time, loyalty, qualifications) to outcomes (pay, promotion, recognition, training opportunities) against the input–outcome ratio of relevant others. When employees perceive that their ratio is equal to that of others, the result is a sense of fairness or equity, which promotes satisfaction, motivation, and positive work behaviour. Conversely, when employees perceive that their ratio is lower than that of others, meaning they contribute more yet receive less, they experience inequity, which produces dissatisfaction and motivates efforts to restore balance (Adams, 1965 cited in Robbins & Judge, 2020; Robbins & Judge, 2020).

The core assumption of Equity Theory is that employees are rational evaluators of fairness within their social environment. They constantly compare themselves with referent others such as co-workers, individuals in similar roles in other organisations, or even professional peers outside the public sector (Greenberg, 2011). These comparisons shape their levels of motivation and job satisfaction. For example, an employee who perceives they receive fair pay relative to effort invested and relative to others performing similar work is more likely to exhibit loyalty, commitment, and cooperative behaviour. On the other hand, employees who perceive inequity may reduce their effort, complain, seek transfers, or even leave the organisation altogether (Adams, 1965 cited in Robbins & Judge 2020; Colquitt Lefine & Wesson., 2021).

Equity Theory also outlines psychological and behavioural strategies employees adopt when confronted with perceived inequity. These include changing inputs (reducing effort), changing outcomes (seeking promotion or higher pay), cognitive distortion (reinterpreting the situation to perceive fairness), or changing referent others (comparing with a different group). Employees may also engage in withdrawal behaviours such as absenteeism or resignations (Robbins & Judge, 2020). Through these mechanisms, the theory helps explain why perceived fairness is strongly linked to job satisfaction, organisational commitment, and harmonious employee relations.

Contemporary organisational scholarship has extended the theory by highlighting that fairness perceptions involve not just distributive justice (fairness of outcomes) but also procedural justice (fairness of decision-making processes) and interactional justice (quality of interpersonal treatment) (Colquitt et al., 2021). Although these additions do not originate from Adams' formulation, they complement the core insights of Equity Theory and address some of its limitations.

Despite its wide application, Equity Theory has drawn several criticisms. Scholars argue that the theory focuses predominantly on distributive justice (inputs and outcomes), while neglecting other important dimensions of organisational justice such as procedural and interpersonal fairness (Greenberg, 2011). The assumption that employees select clear and comparable referent

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groups has also been questioned, as employees' referents vary widely depending on culture, personal experiences, or organisational hierarchy. This makes the prediction of fairness perceptions more complex than the theory suggests (Colquitt et al., 2021).

Another criticism is that Equity Theory tends to treat employees as rational and consistent in their evaluations of fairness, whereas in reality fairness perceptions are affected by emotions, personality traits, and contextual factors (Robbins & Judge, 2020). Finally, the theory is sometimes criticised for being developed largely from Western organisational contexts, raising concerns about its universality in societies with collectivist orientations. Nonetheless, research across cultures continues to show that fairness is a universal human concern, lending enduring relevance to the theory.

The application of Equity Theory to the Akwa Ibom State Civil Service is highly relevant given the structure of public sector employment in Nigeria. Civil servants often compare their inputs and outcomes not only within ministries and departments but also with employees in other states and even in the federal civil service. Issues such as delayed promotions, salary disparities, insufficient recognition, and irregular allowances are recurring themes in Nigerian public-sector employment and strongly influence fairness perceptions (Adebayo & Ogunsina, 2017).

In conclusion, Equity Theory provides a valuable framework for understanding how perceptions of

fairness shape job satisfaction and employee relations within the Akwa Ibom State Civil Service. The theory explains why civil servants' reactions to pay, promotion, and recognition systems are crucial determinants of their commitment and overall satisfaction. Although the theory has limitations, particularly in failing to address procedural and interactional justice, its foundational insights remain applicable. For a study focused on employee relations and job satisfaction, Equity Theory offers both conceptual clarity and empirical relevance.

Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory

According to Robbins and Judge (2020), Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory, also known as the Motivation–Hygiene Theory, was first propounded in 1959 following a major study by Frederick Herzberg, Bernard Mausner, and Barbara Snyderman on the sources of satisfaction and dissatisfaction among employees. The theory is one of the most influential frameworks in organisational behaviour and provides insight into how workplace conditions shape employees' feelings, motivation, and performance.

Herzberg and his colleagues argued that the factors leading to job satisfaction are different from those leading to job dissatisfaction. They used the critical incident technique to analyse employees' descriptions of times they felt exceptionally good or bad about their jobs. Based on these responses, they concluded that job attitudes arise from two distinct sets of factors: motivators (intrinsic factors) and hygiene factors

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(extrinsic factors) (Robbins & Judge 2020). The core ideas of the theory are as follows:

i. Motivators (Satisfiers)

Motivators are job-content factors that produce satisfaction and increase an employee's intrinsic motivation. They relate to the nature of the work itself and include: Achievement, Recognition, Responsibility, Advancement, Personal growth and the meaningfulness of the work. When these factors are present, employees tend to be more satisfied, productive, and committed to organisational goals (Herzberg, 1966 cited by Robbins & Judge 2020). For example, opportunities for growth can make employees feel valued and invested in, increasing both morale and performance.

ii. Hygiene Factors (Dissatisfiers)

Hygiene factors are job-context elements that, if inadequate, cause dissatisfaction but, if adequate, do not necessarily create satisfaction. These include: salary, job security, working conditions, interpersonal relations, organizational policies, and quality of supervision. The presence of hygiene factors reduces complaints and stabilises employee attitudes, but true satisfaction requires motivators (Herzberg et al., 1959). For example, improving working conditions can eliminate dissatisfaction but does not automatically energise employees to work harder.

iii. Dual-Continuum Assumption

A foundational proposition of the theory is that satisfaction and dissatisfaction are not opposite

ends of a single continuum. Instead, they operate independently: the absence of dissatisfaction does not imply satisfaction, and the absence of satisfaction does not imply dissatisfaction (Robbins & Judge, 2020).

Despite its wide influence, Herzberg's theory has been subject to several criticisms.

i. **Methodological Weaknesses:** One criticism concerns Herzberg's use of the critical incident technique, which tends to encourage self-serving bias. Employees often attribute success to internal factors (their abilities or achievement) and dissatisfaction to external conditions (policies, supervisors) (Ewen, 1964). This could distort the categorisation of motivators and hygiene factors.

ii. **Ambiguity of Factors:** Some researchers argue that certain factors can function as both motivators and hygiene factors depending on the context. For instance, salary may motivate employees in some situations but may act only as a hygiene factor in others. This overlap challenges the distinct separation proposed by Herzberg.

iii. **Individual and Cultural Differences:** Herzberg's theory assumes that all employees react similarly to motivators and hygiene factors. However, employees' values, personalities, socio-economic background, and cultural context influence what they perceive as satisfying or dissatisfying (Miner, 2005). This limits the universality of the model.

iv. **Applicability to All Job Types:** Herzberg's original research was conducted with

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engineers and accountants—professional groups with autonomy and growth opportunities. Critics argue that the theory is less relevant to routine, clerical, or low-skill jobs where intrinsic motivators may be limited (Robbins & Judge, 2020).

Despite these criticisms, the theory remains useful because it emphasises the importance of meaningful work and intrinsic motivation alongside adequate working conditions.

In a study examining employee relations and job satisfaction in the Akwa Ibom State Civil Service, Herzberg's theory can support the development of conceptual and empirical frameworks and the understanding how both intrinsic job elements and extrinsic workplace conditions shape civil servants' attitudes. Finally, Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory offers a valuable framework for analysing job satisfaction and employee relations in the Akwa Ibom State Civil Service. While extrinsic (hygiene) factors can reduce dissatisfaction and prevent conflict, intrinsic (motivator) factors are essential for building satisfaction, commitment, and positive employee–management relationships. Despite its noted limitations, Herzberg's model remains a relevant and practical tool for understanding the dynamics of workplace attitudes in the public sector.

Research Methodology

This study adopts a survey research design. This design is suitable because it enables the researcher to collect data from a large population and describe the existing conditions, opinions,

and relationships between employee relations practices and job satisfaction in the Akwa Ibom State Civil Service. The survey approach allows for quantitative analysis of variables and helps determine the influence of employee relations on job satisfaction.

The population of the study comprises all civil servants in the Akwa Ibom State Civil Service. This includes employees across different directorates, cadres, and ministries. This consists of 55,120 employees working with the Akwa Ibom State Civil Service drawn from the office of Head of Service, Akwa Ibom State (2025).

According to Wimmer and Dominick (2014), a sample size is needed when a study's population is too large for direct observation. Given the population of this study, the sample size was determined using Yaro's formula propounded by Taro Yamane in 1967.

The formula is given as:

$$N = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Where n = sample size sought

N = population size

e = Margin of error

1 = unity (a constant)

$$\text{Therefore, } n = \frac{55,120}{1+55,120(0.5)^2}$$

$$= 55,120$$

$$1+55,120 \times 0.0025$$

$$= 55,120$$

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55,121 x 0.0025

= 55,120

137.80

= 400

Sample size = 400

The study adopted a multistage sampling procedure consisting of stratified and simple random sampling techniques. First, the Akwa Ibom State Civil Service was stratified into ministries, departments, and agencies (MDAs) based on functional similarities. This provided a clear structure for grouping employees into homogeneous sub-units.

In the second stage, proportionate stratified sampling was used to determine the number of respondents selected from each ministry or agency. The proportion of respondents drawn from each stratum corresponded to its population size within the overall civil service workforce. This ensured fairness and adequate representation of all units.

Finally, simple random sampling (balloting method) was applied within each stratum to select individual workers who participated in the study. This method minimised sampling bias and ensured that every civil servant in the population had an equal chance of being included in the sample. The procedure was appropriate because it increased representativeness and enhanced the validity of the findings.

Data collected was analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics (frequency tables, percentages, mean scores) was

used to answer the research questions. While, inferential statistics such as Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) or Regression Analysis was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. These statistical methods were appropriated to determine relationships between employee relations practices and job satisfaction.

Data Presentation, Analysis and Discussion of Findings

Data Presentation and Analysis

This section of the research exercise considered the presentation, computation and analysis of the raw data with the intention of producing a synthesised result. The data presented in this section were those acquired through the administration and retrieval of the questionnaire from the objectively and systematically selected employees of the Akwa Ibom State Civil Service in their different ministries and agencies. The results of the raw facts were tabulated and their computations carried out using simple percentage. The hypothesis of this study was tested using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC). These set of research activities were conducted for the purpose of achieving the objectives of the study; answering the research questions raised by the study and drawing inferences on the level of relationship existing between the variables of the study via the hypothesis formulated at the beginning of the study.

For records, Three Hundred and Ninety-Seven (400) copies of the questionnaire were

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administered to employees from the Nine (9) Ministries and the Agency of the Akwa Ibom State Civil Service, who formed the respondents of this study. Of the 400 copies administered on

the respondents, three hundred and seventy-two were returned, representing a 93% response rate, which was adequate for analysis.

Table 1: Respondents' Grade Levels in their Work Place

Response	Frequency	Percentage
4-6	100	27
7-10	158	42
11-14	92	25
15 and above	22	6
Total	372	100

Source: Researcher's Field Survey (2025)

The data on Table 1 show that workers within grade level 7-10 (42%), had the highest representation in the sample of this study.

Table 2: Respondents' Year of Service

Response	Frequency	Percentage
1-7	82	22
8-12	140	38
13-19	120	32
20 and above	30	8
Total	372	100

Source: Researcher's Field Survey (2025)

The data on Table 2 show that majority of the respondents in the study (70%) have worked in the Akwa Ibom State Civil Service for over 8-19

years. This means that respondents have prolonged year of service to understand the subject of discourse.

Table 3: Respondents' Ministry/Department/Agency (MDA):

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Information & Strategies	70	19
Finance	60	16
Trade and Investment	45	12
Ministry of Works	46	12
Agriculture and Rural Development	45	12

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Labour and Manpower Planning	40	11
Bureau of Political and Social Re-Orientation	22	6
Women Affairs and Social Welfare	44	12
Total	372	100

Source: Researcher's Field Survey (2025)

The distribution on the Table 3 shows that majority (35%) of the respondents were from the ministry of Information and Strategies and finance.

Table 4: Employee Relations Practice in AKSCS

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Friendly condition and term of employment	-	-
Allowing employee to make contribution during staff meeting	89	24
Award of excellence to outstanding staff	60	16
Improvement of employee morale through incentives	-	-
Institution of crisis or conflict control mechanism	100	27
Building reputable organisational culture	123	33
Total	372	100

Source: Researcher's Field Survey (2025)

The data on Table 4 indicate different employee relations activities carried out in the Akwa Ibom State Civil Service. The analysis showed that the most practiced employee relations in AKSCS

with 60% is building reputable organisational culture and institutional of crisis or conflict control mechanism.

Table 5: Employee Relations practices that influences Job Satisfaction most in AKSCS

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Smooth flow of Information between management staff and employees.	70	19
Openness and transparency in communication	50	13
Fair and objective leadership	52	14
Participation in decision making	-	-
Fair distribution of rewards and allowance	80	22
Recognition of hardworking employees	45	12
Prompt conflict resolution without bias	35	9
Effective grievance handling procedure	40	11
Total	372	100

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Source: Researcher's Field Survey (2025)

The distribution on Table 5 shows that fair distribution of rewards and allowance and smooth flow of information between management staff and employee in in the Akwa

Ibom State Civil Service (41%) is the employee relations' practice that enhances their job satisfaction most.

Table 6: Response on if current Employee Relations practice enhances Job Satisfaction in AKSCS

Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Total Score	N	3.0 WMS	Decision
Employee relations practice enhances job satisfaction	152	90	60	70	1068	372	2.87	Negative/Rejected

Source: Researcher's Field Survey (2025)

Data presented on Table 6 indicates with a WMS of 2.87 that current employee relations practice in AKSCS does not enhance job satisfaction.

Table 7: Extent to which Employee Relations influences Job Satisfaction in AKSCS

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Very Great Extent	132	35
Great Extent	160	43
Little Extent	50	13
Very Little Extent	30	9
Total	372	100

Source: Researcher's Field Survey (2025)

The distribution on Table 7 shows that 78% of respondents agreed that job satisfaction in this

study is to a very great extent influenced by the employee relations practices of AKSCS.

Table 8: Strategies that can improve Employee Relations and Enhance Job Satisfaction in AKSCS

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Strengthen Communication Channels	72	19
Ensure Transparent and Timely Promotion processes	90	24
Improve Welfare and Reward System	50	13

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Improve the work Environment	60	16
Invest in Training and Career Development	100	28
Total	372	100

Source: Researcher's Field Survey (2025)

The distribution on Table 8 shows that strategies that can improve employee relations in AKSCS are invest in training and career development

Testing of the Research Hypothesis

H₁: There is no significant relationship between employee relations and job satisfaction in the Akwa Ibom State Civil Service

H₂: There is a significant relationship between employee relations and job satisfaction in the Akwa Ibom State Civil Service.

The Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient Parametric test was used for the testing of the hypothesis of this study. The variables (employee relations and job satisfaction) are continuous. The data were

Table 9: Correlation between Employee Relations and Job Satisfaction in the Akwa Ibom State Civil Service

Employ ee Relation s X	Job Satisfacti on Y	X ²	Y ²	XY	r Calculat ed	r critic al	D f	Significa nt level	Decisio n
152	132	23,104	17,424	20,064	0.31	0.27	3	0.05	
90	160	8,100	25,600	14,400					
60	50	3,600	2500	3,000					
70	30	4,900	900	2,100					
$\sum X = 372$	$\sum Y = 372$	$\sum X^2 = 39,704$	$\sum Y^2 = 46,424$	$\sum XY =$					

and ensure transparent and timely promotion processes of employees.

gotten from tables 4.1.9(X) and 4.1.10(Y) respectively, where X contained the distribution on employee job satisfaction in the civil service and Y contained the distribution on whether employee relations led to job satisfaction of the employees in the civil service. The study sought to determine the strength and direction of relationship between the two variables and the hypothesis were tested at 0.05 level of significance. This computation is presented in the table below:

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				39,56					
				4					

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey (2025)

The formula for Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient is as in Equation 4.1 PPMCC:

$$r = \frac{N\sum XY - (\sum X)(\sum Y)}{\sqrt{[N\sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2][N\sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2]}}$$

Equation 4.1

Where

r = Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient

\sum = Summation

$\sum x$ = Sum of the X original scores on influence of employee relations on job satisfaction = 372

$\sum y$ = Sum of the Y original scores on employee job satisfaction = 372

$\sum x^2$ = Sum of the X scores = 39,704

$\sum y^2$ = Sum of the squared Y scores = 46,424

$\sum xy$ = Sum of the product of each X and Y = 39,564

N = Number of the paired scores.

Df = N-2, i.e. 5-2 = 3

Therefore df = 3

Decision Rule: If the calculated r is greater than the table value ‘r’ at 0.05 level of significance for a two-tailed test with degree of freedom (df) (n-1) (n-2), the null hypothesis accept and reject the alternate hypothesis and vice versa. The null hypothesis state that there is no significant relationship between employee

relations and job satisfaction in Akwa Ibom State Civil Service.

Following the decision rule, the calculated “r” value of 0.31 is significantly greater than the critical value of “r” 0.27, the hypothesis which state that there is a significant relationship between employee relations and job satisfaction in Akwa Ibom state Civil Service is accepted.

Discussion of Findings

The discussion of findings of this study centered solely on the data generated from the field work precisely from the questionnaire designed for the study which emanated from the three (3) research questions raised at the preliminary stage of this study.

Research Question 1: What employee relations practices are carried out in the Akwa Ibom State Civil Service?

This question was aimed at finding out whether there are any employee relations practice(s) carried out in the Akwa Ibom State Civil Service. The answer to this research question is provided by the data on table 4. On table 5 were displayed the different employee relations practices upheld in Akwa Ibom State Civil Service. From the data, 60% of respondents agreed that it is building reputable organisational culture, and institution of crisis or conflict control mechanism.

This data set is a depiction of the reality that employee relations is an existing organisational or corporate practice in the Akwa Ibom State

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Civil Service. The data have shown that employee relations in the AKSCS is built on a singular activity, but on a synchronisation of many activities. Greater attention is shown on the response that building reputable organisational culture is one of the practices in government establishments in the state. This describes the value placed on reputable organisational culture by the management of the Akwa Ibom State Civil Service. Okorie (2019) has noted that this kind of communication culture entails the strategic interaction of all aspects of an organisation in a way that enhances organisational productivity, accommodating culture and improved employee involvement in the affairs of the organisation. Ekong (2018) submits that internal organisation communication is a coordination of existing relationships between internal organs of the organization in a way that makes the organization achieve better productivity through employees' performance.

Robbins and Judge (2020) define organisational culture as a shared values, beliefs, norms, assumptions, and ways of behaving that influence how employees think, feel, and act within an organisation. It shapes how work is done, how decisions are made, how employees relate with management and colleagues, and how the organisation responds to internal and external challenges. A culture that emphasises fairness, transparency, mutual respect, and participation tends to promote harmonious employee relations, while a rigid or authoritarian culture may heighten mistrust, grievances, and

industrial unrest. Beyond organisational culture, the data also points out staff welfare, involvement in decisions making to create a sense of belonging, and compensation for the contributions made in organisations. Worlu et al., (2016) submit that providing enabling work environment helps retain employees via meeting their psychological and physical needs.

Discussion on the practices of employee relations have been a significant issue on the table of scholars and researchers. Schein (2017) maintain that employee relations practice expedites greater commitment of employees to the organisation and also facilitate their motivation towards sincere diligence to support the effectiveness of their organisation or company. Such practices allow high-potential employees to become more agile, a skill required in the increasing competition in modern business world. This helps also in expanding the capacity of employees towards higher leadership responsibilities and positions. Jonathan (2020), Verlindeh (2021), and Ciraldo (2021) have, in their different submissions made explanations on the 21st century obtainable employee relations practices among organisations in the world. For instance, Verlinden (2021) outlines some of the employee relations practices to include: dialogue and communication, focus on company mission and values, help employees feel valued, inspire and reward employees, promote health and work-life balance, offer career development, pay attention to work hours and wages issues.

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The findings above also highlight the issue of conflict management as well as employee safety at work place. Guest (2017) suggests that conflict is inevitable, natural and found in workplace dynamics even in the most reputable workplaces. People perceive differently views about situations and try to convince the other people to think as them. Thus, frequent conflicts begin when; there are open communication barriers, when people feel perceived threat or related to the status of their employment, or when they are prevented from meeting the needs of their workplace. At the instance of the findings of this study, the organisation under this study, makes provision for conflict management and safe environment for work, through employee relations practices. The findings (as expressed above) are explained by the theory of social change propounded by Homan. The theory proposes that social behaviour is the result of an exchange process. According to Fajana (2020), the purpose of this exchange is to maximise benefits and minimise costs. As people weigh the benefits of a relationship against the costs of the relationship, they do so by establishing a comparison level that often influenced by social expectations and past experiences.

At the instance of the findings above, the theory explains the place of 'give and take' as a means of finding or experiencing satisfaction. The employees of AKSCS give their time, expertise, and other energy in performing tasks assigned by the civil service and in return expects a good rewarding relationship from the service in

exchange for their resources. Just like Cherry (2019) argues that where there is equilibrium in the level of commitment to relationship, social exchange is higher than when there is lopsidedness and lack of mutuality between parties in a relationship, so are the employees able to achieve satisfaction in the jobs when there is equilibrium in the exchange of values between them and the civil service in Akwa Ibom State. Form from the above discussion, it is therefore inferred that there are different employee relations practices obtainable in the Akwa Ibom State Civil Service. These practices are building organisational culture, institution of crisis or conflict mechanism, allowing employee to make contribution during staff meeting, and the award of excellence to outstanding staff.

Research Question 2: Do employee relations practice enhance job satisfaction in the Akwa Ibom State Civil Service?

The aim of this question was to measure or determine if employee relations practice enhance job satisfaction in Akwa Ibom State Civil Service. The preceding findings has shown that employee relations practice enhance job satisfaction. The respondents were tested to determine their job satisfaction enhanced by employee relations. To do this, Table 4.1.9 and 4.1.10 gave insight for a meaningful understanding of the level of job satisfaction enhanced by employee relations in Akwa Ibom State Civil Service.

The distribution on Table 6 analysis the respondents' employee relations practice and job

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satisfaction in Akwa Ibom State Civil Service. Based on the results, with a WMS of 2.87 of the respondents rejected the fact that the current employee relations practice enhanced job satisfaction. To confirm the employee practice that enhances job satisfaction, the data on Table 5 was used to determine that fact. 41% agreed that fair distribution of reward and allowance enhance job satisfaction, and smooth flow of information between management and employees.'

Job satisfaction has remained not only an important aspect of employee priority but equally an issue of priority to scholars. Basumalick (2020) captures a significant aspect of employees' life in discussing what practices makes job satisfaction possible. The author makes it easy to understand that job satisfaction goes beyond just contentment of workers in their daily work lives, but at the same time covers satisfaction with team managers and members, organisational policies, as well as the impacts their works create on their personal lives. An examination of the positive emotional response of people towards the work they are doing becomes very important especially in assessing the reality of human conception of their works and their future aspirations. Robbins and Judge (2020) submit that the kind of feelings employees have towards satisfaction of their work acts as motivation to work. Having smooth and mutually beneficial relationship between employees and an organisation, is one factor that encourages job satisfaction.

Research attention has increased on the relationship between employee relations and job satisfaction, most of which provides empirical backing that employee relations have positive relationship with job satisfaction, which is the stands of this study. A recent study conducted by Stangrecks and Bagienska (2021) on the role of employee relations in shaping job satisfaction in the era of 21st century. Similarly, the finding of this study is consistent with the study conducted by Kanana (2016) on the perceived relationship between employee relations practices and job satisfaction in Swiss port Limited, Kenya. Findings of the study showed good employees relations practice such as honest and open communication, conducive working environment, freedom to use their abilities and skills, as well as inclusion in decisions making processes that affect their existence in the organisation were factors that to a great extent determine their satisfaction in the organisation. Also, Sharma and Jain (2015) stress that since there is a correlation between job satisfaction and employee relations, practices and strategies for employee relations should be considered by managers in the light of veritable activities that improve the work condition and increases the outcome of an organisation. Balozzi and Aman (2014) further stated that there is a strong correlation between employee relations and job satisfaction of employees within organisations. For them, organisations depend on the communication, intelligence, diligence, contributions, creativity of employees for their

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success. Where the management meets the personal needs and problems of employees, they find fulfilment in their workplace and can therefore give in their best towards the performance and productivity of such organisations and firm. In a similar dimension, Aktar and Pangil (2017) argue that organisations that care for their employees and meet their needs through good employee relations practices have their employees charged to offer great contributions towards organisational growth and sustainability. The authors submit that good employee relations have significant influence on job satisfaction of employees. Miraa et al (2019) state that employee relations practices and job satisfaction at different sectors have strong relationship where one affects the other. This led the scholars to the conclusion that because of such effect employee relations have on job satisfaction, organisational performance also benefits from the relationship.

As shown in by the data, it is arguable that as their basic (physiological) needs are satisfied, the assurance provided for the employees' hygiene factors such as job security, salary regularity, prompt promotion, clear communication, good working conditions, and administrative policies fulfills or gives satisfaction and motivation to employees in Herzberg's two-factor theory. (Udo and Akpan 2021). With the fulfilment of Herzberg's theory, it will clarify how working conditions and motivational opportunities shape satisfaction and dissatisfaction. Additionally, it is imperative that the organisation provide

adequate social support to demonstrate appreciation and concern for the employees, (Aktar & Pangil, 2017). These are necessary because job satisfaction spurs employees' drive to deliver expected organisational outcomes specifically within expected standard and time frame. Arising from the above discussion, deduction can be that job satisfaction of civil servants in Akwa Ibom State is to a great extent influence by the employee relations practice of Akwa Ibom State Civil Service.

Research Question 3: To what extent do employee relations practices influence job satisfaction in the Akwa Ibom State Civil Service?

The aim of this question was determined to measure the extent to which employee relations practices influences job satisfaction in the Akwa Ibom State Civil Service. The respondents were tested to measure the extent to which employee relations practices influences them. To determine this, the data on Table 7 shows respondents' perceptions of the extent to which employee relations practice actually influences job satisfaction in the Akwa Ibom State Civil Service. Here, majority of the respondents (78%) indicated that employee relations practices influence job satisfaction to a very great extent, and a great extent.

Based on the results, since 78% of the respondents (very Great Extent + Great Extent) agreed that employee relations practices influence job satisfaction to a high extent, it is concluded that employee relations practices

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influence job satisfaction in the Akwa Ibom State Civil Service to a great extent. Satisfaction at jobs is an important aspect of organisational strength. Table 4.1.14 further shows that there is a correlation between employee relations and job satisfaction in Akwa Ibom State Civil Service. This makes Godec (2017) argues that different physical and mental workloads can consequently trigger stress, frustration or dissatisfaction in employees and can affect job performance. On this ground, it is therefore meaningful to argue that employees with refined sense of job satisfaction have higher motivation, high morale and improved commitment towards work, which in turn positively impacts on the output from tasks and general performance at work place. Udom and Archibong (2021) asserted that job satisfaction is a great subject of discuss in organisations. This is because where there is no satisfaction; an organization cannot achieve its goals. Therefore, priority needs to be given to the issue of employee satisfaction with their jobs through employee relations practices. Conversely, unsatisfied or dissatisfied employees in organisations with reduced motivation and low morlae tend to decline their performance and individual inputs towards work. This, in the long run, limits overall performance and productivity of the entire organization (Basumalick, 2020).

Job satisfaction as an aspect of organisational existence and employee life is a truism in among employees of the Akwa Ibom State Civil Service. Mira, et al (2019) consider the notion of job

satisfaction from the angle that it refers to individual feelings of employees towards the workplace situation about their jobs; or an individual's subjective perspective (perception) which involves the way they think of or consider their employing organisations. In their opinion, Courtney and Younkyoung (2017) argue job satisfaction in the line of pleasurable emotional state that results from the achievement of job values enhanced by employee relations. Employee relations practices such as effective communication, fair leadership, welfare provision, and grievance handling have a very strong influence on job satisfaction among civil servants in Akwa Ibom State. According to Robbins and Judge (2020), improving these practices is therefore critical to enhancing employee morale, commitment, and productivity.

Conclusion

The concept of employee relations as an aspect of public relations has gained increasing research interest in contemporary studies with special attention to how effective communication can better handle staff treatment at their work place, contribute to productivity and job satisfaction. The concept builds more reliance on the functionality of strategic interaction between employees in organisations and how they build strong relationships that affect different concerns and parties. It is somewhat true that employees that are satisfied with their jobs are always the happier and committed ones. For them, assigned tasks are completed with

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dedication and pleasure no matter the kind of organisation (private or government).

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that employee relations play a critical role in shaping job satisfaction in the Akwa Ibom State Civil Service. Where employee relations practices are fair, transparent and inclusive, civil servants tend to exhibit higher levels of satisfaction, commitment and positive work attitudes. Conversely, weak employee relations characterised by poor communication, unresolved grievances and lack of trust between management and employees negatively affect job satisfaction.

The study concludes that although the Akwa Ibom State Civil Service has established employee relations structures, their implementation remains inconsistent and is affected by administrative, institutional and attitudinal challenges. Addressing these issues is

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essential for improving job satisfaction and enhancing the overall effectiveness of the civil service.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are made:

- i. Management should establish regular and transparent communication systems that allow employees to freely express concerns and receive timely feedback.
- ii. Based on the finding that the current employee relations practice at AKSCS, does not enhance job satisfaction government should carry out a periodic employee relations audit in order to determine current employee relations practices for enhancement of job satisfaction.
- iii. The government should improve employee welfare packages, including health benefits, housing schemes and recognition programmes, to boost job satisfaction.

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